

International Journal of Speech and Audiology

E-ISSN: 2710-3854
P-ISSN: 2710-3846
IJSA 2024; 5(2): 01-05
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[www.rehabilitationjournals.com/
speech-and-audiology-journal](http://www.rehabilitationjournals.com/speech-and-audiology-journal)
Received: 03-05-2024
Accepted: 04-06-2024

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Exploring the influence of face masks and social distancing on mild hearing loss: A study from 2019 to 2023

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of face masks and social distancing on individuals with mild hearing loss (MHL) from 2019 to 2023. The increase in MHL cases during 2020 and 2021 suggested a possible link to COVID-19 safety protocols. A retrospective study using a self-developed questionnaire was conducted among 121 participants with MHL, comparing communication difficulties in scenarios with and without face mask usage and social distancing. Results indicated significantly higher communication challenges when face masks and distancing were enforced, with a combined difficulty score significantly higher in face mask and social distancing conditions. This suggests that COVID-19 protocols increased self-awareness of mild hearing loss, prompting more individuals to seek audiological evaluations. The study concludes that mask usage and social distancing increased communication difficulties for those with MHL, highlighting the importance of addressing these challenges in public health strategies.

Keywords: Mild hearing loss, COVID-19, face masks, social distancing, communication difficulties

Introduction

In the current pandemic of coronavirus, health and government officials are encouraging, even mandating, community-wide face mask wearing and social distancing to reduce the spread of coronavirus. There are three major categories of masks being used to limit the airborne transmission of large respiratory droplets and infectious agents: a respirator, or filtering face piece, such as an N95 mask; medical face masks, such as a surgical or procedure mask; and nonmedical masks, such as commercially or self-made masks usually made of cloth or other textiles. Based on mechanistic plausibility and the desire to reduce SARS-CoV-2 transmission and community impact, universal masking and social distancing are recommended as a means of source control of both symptomatic and asymptomatic individuals to prevent the spread of infectious respiratory droplets to others ^[1].

Mild Hearing Loss: Bilateral MHL can be defined broadly to include a three-frequency pure-tone average (PTA; 0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 kHz) threshold ≥ 25 and ≤ 40 dBHL or thresholds > 25 dBHL at one or more frequencies above 2 kHz in both ears ^[2]. In MHL, one-on-one conversations are fine but the client having difficulty understanding some words when there's a lot of background noise. MHL¹ is one of the factors that can negatively affect speech intelligibility. This may be the consequence of missing speech cues due to reduced audibility or of distortions due to supra-threshold factors related to hearing impairment ^[3]. MHL might not have a problem in a fast-speech environment, but could have considerable difficulty in a noisy one ^[4].

Phonemic restoration effect: Persons with hearing loss uses phonemic restoration effect as a top-down approach to compensate for missed phonemes or missed words in a sentence. Phonemic restoration effect is a perceptual phenomenon where under certain conditions, sounds actually missing from a speech signal can be restored by the brain and may appear to be heard i.e., the brain tends to fill the absent phonemes. MHL individuals could benefit from phonemic restoration, moderately HI individuals could not ^[5]. This observation implies that in mild hearing impairment, top-down mechanisms can still be effectively used.

However, as the degree of hearing impairment increases, these mechanisms seem to lose their effect.

Facial expression and lip-reading aid in understanding speech better: The distorted speech sometimes remains intelligible due to the acoustic and linguistic redundancy in speech signals, where speech cues are coded in multiple ways, and the rich sentential context, which provides additional information for resolving lexical ambiguity [6]. Hence, speech with missing segments can be perceptually restored using the acoustic and linguistic content of the audible speech segments, either locally or globally, using context [7]. The top-down restoration can be so strong that, under specific circumstances, listeners may not even be aware of the missing part of a speech signal.

Lip-reading can also play an important role in helping to alleviate the majority of moderate to severe impairments acquired post-lingually. Its success in this role depends upon the ability of perceivers to relate what they see to what they hear. This is where the analysis must start. When perceiving speech audio-visually observers select place information from vision; manner and voicing information from audition [8].

Increased incidence of MHL cases from 2019 and 2023: The database of MHL cases in AUH and nearby Audiology clinics in Delhi NCR region was compared across previous five years data and it was found that, in 2020 and 2021, the incidence of MHL was significantly high as compared to 2017, 2018 and 2019.

Fig 1: Number of cases (year wise)

During COVID-19 pandemic time, peoples are using mask and following social distancing. As a result, the speech cues that are necessary to trigger the compensatory cognitive mechanisms are not adequately transmitted.

Methods

This is a retrospective study design to associate the possible cause for a surge of MHL in the AUH during COVID-19 time. Questionnaire method was used in the study.

Participants

The database of the clinic was reviewed for a period of five years, from 2019 to 2023. During this period, the number of Mild Hearing Loss (MHL) cases identified were as follows: 2019 (23 cases), 2020 (63 cases), 2021 (58 cases), 2022 (45 cases), and 2023 (33 cases). An increased number of MHL cases was observed in the years 2020 and 2021. The clients with MHL in atleast one ear were selected from the database of AUH. These participants were the active members of the society who visit many noisy and quiet places. A total of 121 participants aged 35-55 years (mean age, 41 ± 2.6 years) were selected for the study who met the inclusion criteria. Participants with MHL in at least one ear and no normal hearing in other ear were included in the study.

Development and Validation of the Questionnaire

A self-developed questionnaire related to communication difficulties was developed and validated. The questionnaire consisted of two sets of closed-ended questions based on two different situations. Situation I contain 10 questions related to communication difficulties during interaction with people who follows social distancing and use face mask. Situation II contains 10 questions related to communication difficulties during interaction with people who do not follows social distancing and do not use face mask. A pilot study was conducted prior to data collection. The research team comprised three audiologists and one research assistants. The research assistant was required to administer the questionnaire on five participants who met the same inclusion criteria as for the main study. The objectives of the pilot study were to ensure the face and content validity of the questionnaire as well as to ensure that there were no discrepancies with regard to the documentation of participant responses. Based on the communication difficulty, the participants were requested to rate the questions in a four-point rating scale i.e., “Always”, “Mostly”, “Rarely” & “Never”. Where “Always” is the response for maximum communication difficulty and “Never” is the response for no communication difficulty. The response “Always” and “Mostly” is the indication of

communication difficulty the response “Rarely” and “Never” is the indication of less/no communication difficulty.

Distribution of the Questionnaire

The questionnaire was designed to be comprehensive and user-friendly, and it was distributed in the form of a Google-form link to all MHL cases from the years 2020 and 2021 (a total of 63±58=121 cases). The link of questionnaire was distributed via WhatsApp and email to ensure maximum reach and convenience for the participants.

Data Collection

Participants were requested to complete the Google Form within one month of receiving the questionnaire. Reminders were sent as necessary to encourage participation. A total of 74 completed questionnaires were received from the participants. This represents a response rate of approximately 61.2%.

Statistical Analysis

The responses were collected and subjected to statistical

analysis. The responses were analyzed using independent sample t-test for communication difficulties between the two situations.

Results

Responses of participants were compared for situation I and II. The number of responses i.e., “always”, “mostly”, “rarely” & “never” was counted individually. For situation I, the responses are 24.3%, 49%, 23.7% and 3% for always, mostly, rarely and never respectively. For situation II, the responses are 7%, 17.7%, 47.6% and 34% for always, mostly, rarely and never respectively. The combined response (always + mostly) for situation I (M=3.67, SD=1.8) was compared to the situation II (M=0.91, SD=1.49) using independent sample t-test. The response for communication difficulties was significantly high in situation I, T(146)=9.06, P=0.0 Bar graph of responses obtained for situation I and situation II questionnaire are displayed in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively. Figure 3 displays bar graph of combined response (always + mostly) for situation I & II.

Fig 2: Showing responses of situation 1 questionnaire

Fig 3: Showing responses of situation 2 questionnaire

Fig 4: Showing comparison of communication difficulty at situation I and II

Discussion

In the present study, the communication difficulties across two different situations were compared using questionnaire method and it was observed that communication difficulties were significantly high in situation I, where people were using face mask and follow social distancing. These findings suggest that the self-realization of MHL was high due to COVID-19 safety protocols like social distancing and face mask, this motivates them to visit Audiology clinics for evaluation and rehabilitation. This is due to the degradation of speech cues due to face masking and social distancing. More communication difficulty at situation I indicates that the clients with MHL are facing more difficulties to understand the speech of other person. Before the year 2020 and after 2021, use of face mask and social distancing of 6 feet was not compulsory for everyone, so the clients with MHL compensate their hearing loss by using their cognition and other facial cues of speaker to fill up the missed syllables in the words and understand the verbal message. But in 2020, 2021 and mid-2022, because of COVID-19, people were using face masks and follows social distancing of at least 6 feet. The use of face mask degrades speech quality and denies important visual clues (example, lip reading, facial expressions), and a loss of 3-4 dB in intensity has been viewed in medical mask and nearly 12 dB loss for N95 mask [1, 9]. The conversational distances between two talkers ranges from 1.5 to 3 feet, and for maintaining social distancing, the recommended distance is atleast 6 feet (which translates to a doubling or even quadrupling of the distance) so according to inverse square law, the sound pressure level decreases by 6 to 12 dB [1, 10]. Along with this, the use of face mask provides more attenuation in high frequencies, which are responsible for the clarity of speech [11]. This reduction in intensity and unavailability of important facial cues further increase the problem of clients with MHL to understand the speech. The use of face mask reduces the speech intelligibility and word recognition in listener with hearing loss and listener with normal hearing in poor listening situations [12]. During COVID-19 period, reduction in social interaction and speech audibility was observed especially in the individuals with hearing

impairment [13].

This study examined the communication difficulties of patients with MHL in various situations. It is observed that the communication difficulty increases as people around them follows COVID 19 safety protocols i.e., face mask and a social distancing of at least 6 feet.

Summary and Conclusion

During the year 2020, 2021 and mid-2022, people use face-masks and follow social distancing, which in turn decreases external cues to understand the verbal message. This will further increase the problem of MHL clients to understand the verbal message. This communication breakdown will make them realize about their hearing loss, which motivates them to visit audiology clinic for hearing evaluation and rehabilitation.

Acknowledgment

The authors would like to acknowledge all the participants and Amity University Haryana in this research.

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